

A NOTE ON THE VOLUMETRIC ESTIMATION OF LEAD.

BY PARES CHANDRA BANERJEE.

Lead iodate, as is well known, is sparingly soluble in water. Alfred and Coolbaugh (*J. Soc. Chem Ind.*, 1873, 6, 398) worked out a process for the volumetric estimation of lead based upon the precipitation of lead from its solution after slightly acidifying it with nitric acid, with a solution of potassium iodate and then boiling for a few minutes. The precipitate of lead iodate after filtration is dissolved in dilute hydrochloric acid and then titrated in the presence of chloroform with a standard solution of ammonium thiocyanate to the first appearance of violet colour in chloroform. This method, however, suffers from the drawback that small amount of lead iodate tends to pass into solution in time of washing out the excess of potassium iodate.

To avoid the loss of lead iodate during washing the metal has been precipitated by the author as iodate with a moderate excess of a standard solution of potassium iodate excess of which is determined iodometrically by titrating with sodium thiosulphate. The volume of the precipitated lead iodate may seem to cause some error, but this is negligible as the density of lead iodate is 5.4 and its volume never exceeds 0.1-0.2 c.c.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Lead nitrate (28.2921 g.) purified by recrystallisation were dissolved in water and the solution made up to one litre. Its strength was also determined by estimating its lead content as sulphate. A known volume of this solution was taken in a 100 c.c. flask and was diluted with water to about 25 c.c. A measured volume of standard potassium iodate solution (N) was added drop by drop from a burette with constant shaking till complete precipitation. Then a few c.c. more of potassium iodate varying from 1 to 10 c.c. were added. The mixture was then made up to 100 c.c., cooled in ice and filtered and in an aliquot part of the filtered solution, excess of iodate was determined by titrating with a standard solution of thio-sulphate. The results are given in the following table.

1 C.c. of $N/10$ - KIO_3 soln. = 0.01726 g. of Pb. $Na_2S_2O_3$ soln. = 0.9961 $N/10$.
 1 C.c. of $Pb(NO_3)_2$ soln. = 0.01766 g. of Pb.

Pb $(NO_3)_2$ soln.	KIO_3 added.	$Na_2S_2O_3$ reqd. by excess of KIO_3 .	Amount of Pb	
			Found.	Calc.
10 c.c.	12 c.c.	18.0 c.c.	0.1762 g.	0.1766 g.
10	12	17.0	0.1765	"
10	20	98.0	0.1767	"
10	20	98.4	0.1760	"
20	25	45.2	0.3538	0.3532
20	25	45.6	0.3531	"
20	22	16.6	0.3511	"
20	25	46.7	0.3513	"
10	12	18.15	0.1758	0.1766

In the last three determinations lead was precipitated from the hot solution in presence of nitric acid according to Alfred and Coolbaugh's method.

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
 THE UNIVERSITY OF DACCA,
 DACCA.

Received November 11, 1941.